

Release of titanium species from 3D printed gyroid implant of the novel beta alloy TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈

Purpose

Metal implants have a significantly higher elastic modulus than bone, which can lead to difficult osseointegration. One way to adapt them is to use porous structures, but these can lead to an increase in the corrosion rate and the release of increased amounts of metal species into the human body.

Design/methodology/approach

This work focused on the spontaneous release of Ti species from a 3D printed gyroid structure of the beta alloy TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈. The dissolution kinetics were monitored by exposure tests in a physiological saline solution environment with the addition of fluoride (PSF) and minimum essential medium (MEM) followed by Ti determination by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ET-AAS).

Findings

The dissolution rate from the low-grade passive layer in the fluoride environment is controlled by cathodic oxygen reduction. In a fluoride-free environment, the quality of the passive layer is high and dissolution is not dependent on the oxygen content in the environment. Numeric simulations confirmed a sufficient rate of Ti excretion from the bloodstream. The corrosion rate is sufficiently low (215 nm.a⁻¹) even in the more aggressive fluoride-containing environment and does not compromise the mechanical properties and functionality of the implant for a lifetime of 30 a.

Originality

This work dealt a novel beta alloy TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ using processing by modern 3D printing technology into a gyroid structure, which provides the most isotropic mechanical properties of all porous structures.

Keywords: Ti beta alloy, implant, dissolution, electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry

INTRODUCTION

Aerospace alloy TiAl6V4 has a wide range of applications including the manufacture of medical implants (Baehre *et al.*, 2016, Biguetti *et al.*, 2021, Monteiro-Pereira *et al.*, 2021, Wisbey *et al.*, 1991). However, the alloy has a higher elastic modulus that can lead to "stress-shielding" and also its two-phase structure can undergo selective dissolution (Kurtz, 2023, Kurtz *et al.*, 2024). Single-phase alloys with a beta structure

have been developed to reduce the elastic modulus and homogeneity of the corrosion properties (Calazans Neto *et al.*, 2024, Pesode and Barve, 2023). In particular, Mo, Ta or Nb are typical stabilizers of the beta structure of Ti (Boraei *et al.*, 2023, Haswendra, Huang *et al.*, 2018, Chan *et al.*, 2016, Khulief, 2018, Okazaki and Gotoh, 2005, Okazaki *et al.*, 2004, Robin and Carvalho, 2013, Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021). Neutral alloying elements in terms of stabilization are Zr (Haswendra, Huang *et al.*, 2018, Chan *et al.*, 2016, Khulief, 2018, Okazaki and Gotoh, 2005, Okazaki *et al.*, 2004, Robin and Carvalho, 2013, Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021) and Sn (Li *et al.*, 2018), but there are also experiments with exotic Hf (Lin *et al.*, 2017). Sn reduces the cost and is biocompatible (Chen *et al.*, 2020). The TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ alloy used in this work, exhibits an elastic modulus of 32 GPa (Hybasek *et al.*, 2020), which is very close to the elastic modulus of long bones in the human body.

The corrosion rate in the body environment is usually very low; the influence of organic substances is interesting, as some authors have observed a decrease in corrosion rate due to the presence of albumin (Boraei *et al.*, 2023), while others have observed an increase in corrosion rate in the presence of protein (Healy and Ducheyne, 1993). Hiromoto *et al.* observed a decrease in corrosion rate in contact with cells (Hiromoto, 2008). In terms of alloying elements, Nb and Sn are particularly crucial in beta alloys. Ossowska *et al.* consider the diffusion of lattice defects through the passive layer as the controlling phenomenon of corrosion in the steady passive state (Ossowska and Zieliński, 2020). Nb, as a pentavalent cation, compensates for the presence of oxygen vacancies in the passive layer and thus makes its dissolution more difficult (Bai *et al.*, 2012, Macdonald, 2019, Metikos-Hukovic *et al.*, 2003). Sn, on the other hand, has a rather destabilizing effect (Kim *et al.*, 2007). In terms of corrosion, the presence of fluoride in the environment and pH are key factors (Robin and Carvalho, 2013). In the presence of fluorides and low pH, the passive layer on the surface is porous and the dissolution rate of the alloy increases significantly (Anwar *et al.*, 2011, Noubissi *et al.*, 2019).

Besides the addition of suitable alloys and stabilization of the beta structure, another possibility to adjust the elastic modulus of the bone is the hollow profile (Risse *et al.*, 2022) or the manufacturing of porous implant structures (Guo *et al.*, 2022) using 3D printing technology. A question is the possible influence of the 3D printed microstructure on the corrosion properties of the alloy. Qin *et al.* (Qin *et al.*, 2019) compared 3D printed (Selective Laser Melting) and molded TiNb₂₄Zr₄Sn₈ alloy and observed no difference in corrosion behavior in 3.5% NaCl. The same topic was also addressed by our team in previous work (Fojt *et al.*, 2025). In the 3D printed state, the TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ alloy dissolved in physiological saline at a slightly higher rate than the wrought state, but in an aggressive environment with added fluoride and reduced pH, the dissolution of the 3D printed alloy was an order of magnitude slower than that of the wrought variant.

However, the electrochemical techniques used in the aforementioned works provide only approximate information about the actual dissolution of the alloy. More reliable information is provided by exposures with subsequent evaluation of the dissolved ions

in solution, including a record of the evolution of dissolution kinetics over time. Indeed, dissolution slows down in a limited volume of solution during exposure, see Fig. 1 (Sotniczuk *et al.*, 2023). Browne *et al.* (Browne and Gregson, 1994, Browne *et al.*, 1996) observed a change in the dissolution kinetics mechanism over time, which they explain as the evolution of the passive layer composition and the subsequent steady state.

Extreme dosing and retention of Ti in the body is usually verified *in vivo* by administering a dose of TiO₂ nanoparticles, with the liver being the main organ for Ti retention (Elgrabli *et al.*, 2015, Fabian *et al.*, 2008, Olmedo *et al.*, 2002, Wang *et al.*, 2007). Examples of literature sources are given in Table 1. Intravenous administration leads to significantly higher retention in the liver. In the work of Elgrabli *et al.* (Elgrabli *et al.*, 2015), even the kinetics of Ti excretion over time was studied. The course of Ti excretion from the liver is shown in Fig. 2. The linear dependence on time is indicative of zero-order kinetics, which is typical for catalyzed reactions or complexing reactions with a constant concentration of complexant (enzyme) in solution.

Tab. 1 Summary of *in vivo* experiments with Ti dosing and retention in liver

Dose TiO ₂ nanoparticles	Lasting in organism	Citation
16 g/kg (intraperitoneal)	still present in liver as particles (5 m)	(Olmedo <i>et al.</i> , 2002)
5 g/kg (gastrointestinal)	liver 4 ug/g (14 d)	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2007)
5 mg/kg (intravenous)	liver 111 ug/g (28 d)	(Fabian <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
9.4 mg/kg (intravenous)	liver 939 ug/organ (1 d); 58 (56 d)	(Elgrabli <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

Fig. 1 Typical kinetics of Ti release into constant volume of solution (Sotniczuk *et al.*, 2023)

Fig. 2 Kinetics of Ti excretion from liver (Elgrabli *et al.*, 2015)

This work focused on the study of the kinetics of Ti release from TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ alloy into the body environment and a theoretical model of dissolution in the geometry of the gyroid structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

The alloy of composition TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ was in powder form with a mean particle size of 60 μm . It was used in two geometries for the experiments. The 3D printed rod had a diameter of 16 mm. Discs of 3 mm height were cut off with it. The gyroid structure was printed with a wall thickness of 500 μm and a porosity of 0.5, and had a cube shape with an edge length of 15 mm (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Gyroid sample after exposure

The first set of exposure experiments was performed with disc samples, each disc exposed in 20 ml of physiological saline solution supplemented with NaF (200 ppm fluoride) and pH adjusted to 4 by HF (solution denoted hereafter as PSF). The exposure times were 1, 2, 4, 7 and 14 days. Oxygen saturation was maintained at 3 levels using a glovebox atmosphere (oxygen, air, nitrogen). After exposure, the test solution was always stabilized with 0.5 ml of HNO₃ (conc.), followed by analysis of the released Ti by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ET-AAS). The oxidation-reduction potential ($E_{\text{RED/OX}}$) on the Pt wire was also measured at all oxygen saturation levels until steady state, followed by measurement of the oxygen content of the solution using an oximeter. Furthermore, the potentiodynamic cathodic curves on the surface of TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ alloy were measured against the free corrosion potential (E_{CORR}) in the range of $+0.05 \text{ V}/E_{\text{CORR}}$ to $-1 \text{ V}/E_{\text{CORR}}$ with a polarization rate of $2 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The reference

electrode was a saturated silver-silverchloride electrode (ACLE) and the counter electrode was a platinum wire.

The second set of experiments had the same setup, but the test solution was Minimal Essential Medium (MEM) Eagle, exposure times were approximately 1, 3, 6, and 12 months, and only 2 oxygen levels (nitrogen, oxygen) were used.

For the third set of experiments, gyroid samples exposed in 6 ml of MEM with an oxygen atmosphere for up to 8 months were used. After exposure, the corrosion products were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis.

RESULTS

The Ti concentrations in the PSF solution as a function of exposure time are shown in Fig. 4, left. The dissolution rate decreases with time, and the concentration versus time dependence is parabolic in nature. The dissolution kinetics is dependent on the oxygen content of the medium, where the dissolution rate of Ti increases with increasing oxygen content. Therefore, the kinetics of the cathodic oxygen reduction reaction itself on the surface of TiNb₂₅Ta₄Sn₈ alloy (see Fig. 5, left) was measured, which exhibits diffusion control and a limiting current density dependent on the oxygen content of the medium.

Fig. 4 Results of Ti concentration measurements in PSF solution (disc sample); raw data (left); data as molar concentration fitted by kinetic model from Discussion section (right)

Fig. 5 Potenciodynamic cathodic curves in PSF solution with different content of oxygen (left); extrapolation of initial Ti dissolution rates up to content of releasable oxygen in blood after the model from Discussion chapter (right)

In the MEM environment, the dissolution of Ti over time is significantly slower (Fig. 6, left), with the system reaching a similar concentration level after approximately 6 months of exposure, compared to 2 weeks in PSF. The dissolution kinetics in this case are independent of the oxygen content of the medium, and solutions purged with both oxygen and nitrogen show the same Ti concentration measurements.

Fig. 6 Results of Ti concentration measurements in MEM solution (disc sample); raw data (left); data as molar concentration fitted by kinetic model from Discussion section (right)

In the case of measurements on samples with gyroid structure, precipitation of solid corrosion products already occurred between 14 and 18 days of exposure, which was not observed in previous cases. In this case, the solution was obviously already supersaturated with Ti species and precipitation of solid Ti species from the solution occurred. Subsequent results from day 18 onwards already show a linear dependence of Ti content on time (in contrast to the previous parabolic dependencies in Figs. 4 and 6), where the kinetics is probably already controlled by solid species precipitation and not by dissolution of Ti from the alloy. For all samples, the solid species of Ti were always transferred back into solution by stabilization with the addition of nitric acid, but in one case the solid particles were filtered out and determined as pure anatase (TiO_2) by X-Ray diffraction (XRD), as shown in Fig. 8. This is consistent with the results of our

previous work (Fojt *et al.*, 2025), which showed that Ti is the main element released from the passive layer, while other alloying elements remain enriched in the passive layer. Nevertheless, the presence of corrosion products of the other alloying elements cannot be excluded, but their content is under XRD detection limit.

The characterization of solid corrosion products formed directly on the surface of the gyroid sample after 8 months of exposure was also performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis. SEM images are shown in Fig. 9. EDS analysis was performed on the surface with corrosion products and on a bare ground surface (Table 2). The results on the bare surface correspond to the composition of the alloy. In addition to all the metal elements of the alloy, the corrosion products contain mainly oxygen, as well as carbon, sulfur, chlorine, sodium, and potassium, which are components of the MEM solution.

Fig. 7 Results of Ti concentration measurements in MEM solution (gyroid sample); raw data (left); data as molar concentration fitted by kinetic model from Discussion section (right)

Fig. 8 XRD pattern of solid precipitates from the experiments of gyroid exposure in MEM (identified as pure anatase-TiO₂)

Fig. 9 SEM images of the gyroid sample after exposure in MEM (8 months); green rectangle in the left image is given in detail in the right image; red rectangle is area of corrosion products EDS analysis given in Tab. 2

Tab. 2 EDS analyses of the surface

Element / Content (wt.%)	Bare surface	Corrosion products
Ti	65.8	27.3
Nb	22.3	11.6
Sn	6.7	3.2
Ta	5.1	1.5
O	-	31.0
C	-	11.8
S	-	4.5
Cl	-	1.9
Na	-	5.8
K	-	1.4

DISCUSSION

Exposures of samples with a gyroid structure resulted in the precipitation of solid corrosion products from the MEM solution after exceeding a Ti concentration of $3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$. This was due to the extreme ratio of sample surface area to small solution volume ($25.7 \text{ cm}^2/6 \text{ cm}^3$) in this experiment compared to previous experiments with disc-shaped samples ($5.5 \text{ cm}^2/20 \text{ cm}^3$). Thus, the above concentration represents the maximum Ti dissolved species content before precipitation of anatase solids.

Therefore, oxidation-reduction potentials ($E_{\text{RED/OX}}$) were also measured, see Table 3. Subsequently, thermodynamic calculations of the concentrations of each dissolved species were performed using freeware Spana in PSF ($150 \text{ mmol.dm}^{-3} \text{ Cl}^-$; $10 \text{ mmol.dm}^{-3} \text{ F}^-$; pH 4) and MEM ($150 \text{ mmol.dm}^{-3} \text{ Cl}^-$; pH 7) solutions. The results are summarized in Fig. 10. $E_{\text{RED/OX}}$ had no significant effect on the results, nor did pH or fluoride content. The main dissolved specie in the MEM environment is TiO(OH)_2 . For comparison, Schmidt et al. published Ti(OH)_4 as the main dissolved specie in a $0.1 \text{ mol.dm}^{-3} \text{ NaCl}$ environment and a pH range of 4 to 8 (Schmidt and Vogelsberger, 2006). In the PSF environment, there is also a relatively high concentration of TiF_6^{2-} , but it is overwhelmed by the concentration of TiO(OH)_2 before the onset of solid phase precipitation. However, upon reaching a TiO(OH)_2 concentration of $3.16 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$, TiO_2 precipitation should theoretically already be occurring indiscriminately in both environments and under all conditions. The difference between this theoretical equilibrium value and the concentration value of $3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$ determined in our experiments may be either kinetic, in the need for significant supersaturation for real-time precipitation, or the existence of a metastable colloidal form.

Tab. 3 $E_{\text{RED/OX}}$ of both solutions after purging with nitrogen, air or oxygen

E (V/SHE)	nitrogen	air	oxygen
MEM	0.437	0.482	0.520
PSF	0.312	0.431	0.482

Fig. 10 Solubility of Ti species in PSF purged by nitrogen (upper left) and oxygen (upper right) and MEM purged by nitrogen (lower left) and oxygen (lower right)

In a PSF environment, the dissolution kinetics of the poor quality passive layer is controlled by the cathodic reaction. As shown in Fig. 5, left, the cathodic reaction is controlled by oxygen diffusion according to Eq. 1, and is directly proportional to the oxygen concentration in the medium. Therefore, the oxygen concentrations in the PSF environment were also measured after steady-state purging by each gas: 0.7 mg.dm⁻³ (nitrogen), 6.7 mg.dm⁻³ (air) and 31.2 mg.dm⁻³ (oxygen). Considering the maximum decrease in blood oxygen saturation (97% → 75%), the maximum amount of oxygen released by the blood is approximately 65 mg.dm⁻³.

$$j_{LIM} = \frac{D \times z \times F \times c_{ox}}{\delta} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

j_{LIM} – limiting current density of oxygen reduction [$A.m^{-2}$]; z – No. of electrons exchanged; F – Faraday constant [$96\,480\,C.mol^{-1}$]; c_{ox} – concentration of oxygen in the solution bulk [$mol.m^{-3}$]; δ – Nernst diffusion layer thickness [m]

The data from Figs. 4, 6 and 7 were converted to molar concentrations and these were subsequently fitted using a numeric simulation with simplifying assumptions for discretisation. This is based on the: infinitely fast transport in the surrounding solution and control of passive layer dissolution limited by increasing concentration in solution (a degree of saturation). For the simulation, the definition of the heterogeneous reaction rate (Eq. 2) and first-order kinetics are assumed to be valid. Discretization into small time steps allows the separation of the variables (Eq. 3). For each step, the concentration is then calculated based on the variables determined in the previous step (Eqs. 4-6).

$$j = \frac{V}{A} \times \frac{dc}{dt} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$dc = j \times \frac{A}{V} \times dt \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$c_i = \left[j_{i-1} \times \frac{A}{V} \times (t_i - t_{i-1}) \right] + c_{i-1} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$j_{i-1} = j_0 \times \Omega_{i-1} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$\Omega_{i-1} = \frac{c_s - c_{i-1}}{c_s - c_0} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

c_i / c_{i-1} – concentration in particular time step [$mol.dm^{-3}$]; c_s – concentration at the saturation [$mol.dm^{-3}$]; c_0 – initial concentration (assumed zero) [$mol.dm^{-3}$]; j_0 – initial dissolution rate into ion free solution [$mol.m^{-2}.s^{-1}$]; j_{i-1} – dissolution rate in particular time step [$mol.m^{-2}.s^{-1}$]; t – time; A – surface area [m^2]; V – volume of solution [dm^3]; Ω_{i-1} – degree of saturation

The input data for the numeric simulation are summarized as follows. Concentration at saturation $c_s = 3.5 \times 10^{-6} mol.dm^{-3}$. For the disk experiments, the exposed area was $5.5\,cm^2$ and the solution volume was $20\,cm^3$. For the gyroid experiments, the solution

volume was 6 cm³. The area was calculated from the S/V ratio for the gyroid structure. This ratio for 0.5 porosity has been published in the range of 2.1 to 7.6 (Dokuz *et al.*, 2021, Timercan *et al.*, 2021, Wallat *et al.*, 2022). Due to the fact that the electrochemically active real surface to geometric surface ratio of 2.4 was determined in previous work (Fojt *et al.*, 2025), a higher S/V factor ratio of 7.6 was conservatively used, and the exposed area of the gyroid sample was thus 25.7 cm². The variable sought to fit the kinetic data was the initial dissolution rate Ti (j_0).

For the PSF solution, this value is dependent on the oxygen content (Fig. 4, right). Values of 3.80×10^{-11} mol.m⁻².s⁻¹ (nitrogen), 1.20×10^{-10} mol.m⁻².s⁻¹ (air) and 3.30×10^{-10} mol.m⁻².s⁻¹ (oxygen) were determined. Since the amount of oxygen released from blood is at the level of 65 mg.dm⁻³, an extrapolation for the blood environment was performed (see Fig. 5, right) to assume a linear dependence of the dissolution rate on the oxygen content (see Eq. 1). The extrapolated value of the initial dissolution rate is 6.46×10^{-10} mol.m⁻².s⁻¹ (blood), which corresponds to a corrosion rate of 215 nm.a⁻¹ and a gyroid wall thickness loss of 430 nm.a⁻¹.

Dissolution in MEM solution is controlled by the slow dissolution of the high-quality passive layer and was not dependent on oxygen concentration. Therefore, only a simulation was performed on the results from MEM purged with oxygen. The determined value of j_0 (Fig. 6, right) was 1.71×10^{-11} mol.m⁻².s⁻¹, corresponding to a corrosion rate of 5.7 nm.a⁻¹, and a gyroid wall loss of 11.4 nm.a⁻¹. This initial dissolution rate was verified and also used for the subsequent fit of the data for the samples with the gyroid structure. As can be seen in Fig. 7 right, these kinetics are generally valid for any geometry and metal surface area/volume ratio of the liquid phase. The kinetics after day 18 of exposure is driven by the precipitation of solid anatase from solution, and is already an order of magnitude slower, corresponding to a Ti steady release rate from the alloy of 8.11×10^{-13} mol.m⁻².s⁻¹.

The results of the dissolution kinetics evaluation from this work are compared with those from other publications in Table 4. Results determined in fluoride-free environments using electrochemical techniques (extrapolation of the Tafel slope) typically overestimate dissolution rate values by several orders of magnitude (Gunawarman *et al.*, 2018, Chan *et al.*, 2016). The results of Sotniczuk *et al.* (Sotniczuk *et al.*, 2023) are slightly higher, although these are results with ex-post analysis of Ti ions after prolonged exposure, the reason may be the extreme oxidizing power of the high peroxide PBS solution compared to the conditions used in this work. The dissolution rate value from Browne *et al.* (Browne and Gregson, 1994) from bovine serum is comparable, but is cumulative over the entire exposure time of 700 h. However, Hanawa *et al.* (Hanawa, 2002) observed a decrease in the impedance modulus value and therefore an increase in the corrosion rate after the addition of bovine serum to MEM.

In a fluoride-containing environment, Noguchi *et al.* (Noguchi *et al.*, 2008) observed a dissolution rate 3 orders of magnitude higher, but in a solution with 4.5-fold higher fluoride content (900 ppm) than that used in this work.

Tab. 4 Comparison of Ti dissolution kinetics of this work and other literature sources

Material	Environment	S/V ratio (cm ² /cm ³)	Time of exposure	Original Value	Method	Recalc Value (mol.m ⁻² .s ⁻¹)	Source
TiAl6V4	Bovine serum	not known	700 h	0.25 ug.cm ⁻² .700h ⁻¹	ion release	2.07 x 10 ⁻¹¹	(Browne and Gregson, 1994)
TiNb35Zr7Ta6	Hank sol.	1/not known	1 h	15.1 uA.cm ⁻²	Tafel slope	3.91 x 10 ⁻⁷	(Chan <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
TiNb29Ta13Zr5	art saliva; pH 5.2	2/600	3 h	0.52 uA.cm ⁻²	Tafel slope	1.35 x 10 ⁻⁸	(Gunawarman <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
TiNb25Ta13Zr5	PBS + H2O2 (0.1 %)	1/1	2 h	2 x 10 ⁻⁵ mmol.cm ⁻² .2h ⁻¹	ion release	2.78 x 10 ⁻⁸	(Sotniczuk <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
			2 d - 14 d	3.2 x 10 ⁻⁴ mmol.cm ⁻² .288h ⁻¹		9.65 x 10 ⁻¹⁰	
TiNb29Ta4Sn8 (disc)	MEM; 40 mg/l O ₂	5.5/20	341 d	-	ion release	1.71 x 10 ⁻¹¹	this work
TiNb29Ta4Sn8 (gyroid)		25.7/6	243 d	-			
TiNb7Al6	PS+NaF (0.2% NaF); pH 3.8	6.3/20	1 h	5 ug.cm ⁻² .h ⁻¹	ion release	2.90 x 10 ⁻⁷	(Noguchi <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
TiNb25Ta4Sn8 (disc)	PS+NaF (200 ppm F-); pH 4; 65mg/l O ₂	4/20	14 d		ion release	6.46 x 10 ⁻¹⁰	this work

To determine the Ti content in the blood and possible retention in the liver, a model (numeric simulation with finite number of elements) was built in COMSOL Multiphysics software that includes blood flow through the implant, Ti release, dilution in the bloodstream and excretion of Ti from the body. The schematic is shown in Fig. 11. The implant was conceived as a continuum with a porosity of 0.5 and a gyroid structure S/V ratio of 7.6 (Wallat *et al.*, 2022). The tortuosity of the gyroid structure with a porosity of 0.5 was then determined to be $\tau = 1.194$ according to the work of Luo *et al.* (Luo *et al.*, 2020). Constrictivity can be neglected for the gyroid structure because the width of the 'tunnel' does not change. The linear velocity of blood flow through the trabecular part of the bone ranges from 16 to 200 $\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (Daish *et al.*, 2017, Kreipke and Niebur, 2017). To achieve maximum Ti saturation in the blood, a lower flow rate of 16 $\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ was chosen (Daish *et al.*, 2017). Total blood volume was calculated as a mean value of 5 dm^3 . For excretion kinetics, data from the work of Elgrabli *et al.* (Elgrabli *et al.*, 2015) were used and are shown in Fig. 2. Assuming the similarity of rat (used in the mentioned work) and human metabolism, and the higher excretion rate of the human body in the ratio of the average liver weight of rats 5 g and humans 1500 g (Treuting *et al.*, 2018), then we get the excretion rate of Ti from the human body at $1.15 \times 10^{-12} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

Two geometries of the 2D implant model were used for the model. For fluoride-containing environments, the maximum dental implant dimensions (to determine the maximum Ti release) were used: 5 mm diameter (Ramos and Mesnard, 2020) and 18 mm length. For MEM environments, the dimensions of the hip implant were used. The model trapezoid porous geometry was used according to the work of Guo *et al.* (Guo

et al., 2022). The length of the porous part was then 100 mm (Darwich *et al.*, 2019) and the width of the lower narrower part was 13 mm (Bologna *et al.*, 2024) in addition to which the upper width of the porous part of the implant (43 mm) was proportionally calculated by digital image analysis (freeware ImageJ) of the implant (Guo *et al.*, 2022).

Fig. 11 Scheme of the model for numeric simulation

Fig. 12 shows the results of the numeric simulation after the steady state is reached, which is for the smaller dental implant in the fluoride environment after 5 min of exposure, while for the larger hip implant in the non-fluoride environment after 37 min of exposure. The maximum blood Ti concentrations achieved are at $1.75 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ for the dental implant and $3.51 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ for the hip implant. Thus, in neither case is the concentration of $3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ necessary for precipitation of solid corrosion products in the form of anatase exceeded, and only soluble Ti species remain in the blood. Moreover, these concentrations in the bloodstream are very rapidly diluted to values close to zero, and significantly lower than the experimentally verified long-term maximum non-toxic Ti speciation in blood of $2.35 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ as reported by Boeckman *et al.* (Boeckmann *et al.*, 2000). As can be seen from Fig. 11, the Ti excretion performance for the two model states considered then maintains the Ti concentration at the model value of zero, and there is no accumulation of Ti species in the bloodstream that could cause precipitation of solid corrosion products over time. This is in agreement with the observation of Lugowski *et al.* (Lugowski *et al.*, 1991), who report identical Ti content in tissues surrounding both full-thickness and porous implants.

For this reason, the corrosion rate on the implant wall is constantly at a maximum level and is not limited by the concentration of Ti species in the blood. However, even so, the observed maximum corrosion rates of 215 nm.a^{-1} (for the dental implant) and 5.7 nm.a^{-1} (for the hip implant) are very low and do not compromise implant function. If the maximum viability of the dental implant of 30 a is considered, then the wall thickness of the gyroid implant is reduced from the original value of $500 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $487 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The change in thickness on the hip implant wall is negligible according to the non-uniformity of 3D printing. The question remains as to how long the implant is actually in contact with the bloodstream. According to Mello-Machado et al. (Mello-Machado *et al.*, 2021), this time is only 28 days until full osseointegration.

Fig. 12 Numeric simulation of dissolution steady state of: dental implant in blood containing fluorides (left) and hip implant in blood without fluorides (right)

CONCLUSIONS

The rate of Ti release from the implant in a fluoride environment is dependent on the content of releasable oxygen in the blood. In a non-fluoride environment, it is then controlled by the slow dissolution of the high-quality passive layer and is independent of the oxygen content. The rate of excretion of Ti species from the human body is sufficiently rapid and does not allow the concentration of Ti species in the blood to increase. Thus, the dissolution of Ti in the human body is not limited over time, as observed in experiments with a constant volume of test solution. Thus, a model fit of the experimental data is required to determine the maximum rate of Ti dissolution in constant volume solution experiments. However, even the highest dissolution rates do not lead to the supersaturation of Ti species leading to the precipitation of anatase-based solid corrosion products, and the loss of the gyroid wall structure does not

significantly compromise the mechanical properties of the implant even in a fluoride containing environment.

Acknowledgement

The work on this paper was supported by the Czech Science Foundation grant No. GA23-04971S and OP JAK project No. CZ.02.01. 01/00/22_008/0004634 (manuscript data are available on this link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17720677>).

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